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**Abstract for the CERN Physics Beyond Colliders
Study Group**

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Quantum Neural Network and cosmological models within humans' [cosmic particles contained within the human being individual's body] - and this cosmological model's comparison with the Dark Matter and dark energy in the entire cosmos.

Quantum Physics is related to neural networks. Quantum Physics is also related to the cosmology and entire cosmos.

Peace and harmony within an individual human being arises due to the balance between

- a) The cosmic particles within the human body and
- b) Against the cosmic particles surrounding this human in the external entire cosmos.

This balancing cosmological qualities and characteristics could be devised in the form of a human cosmological quantum neural network model.

This CQNN [Cosmological Quantum Neural Network] model is functionally and technically created and designed in the form of an information technology product/ application either on the computer or handheld mobile device.

The qualities of the CQNN for that human being individual [who is under study] is then fetched from the product/ application database. Then it is compared with the cosmological i.e dark matter and dark energy model.

This leads to the ideas that provide the solutions for the problem/ issue of "Cosmological harmony required for achieving the life – balance by each and every individual human being"! These ideas could then be progressed upon, to devise projects and proposals, based on the theme of The Sustainable Development and Human Healthcare.